
NON-TRADITIONAL FORMS OF EDUCATION IN THE CURRENT PERIOD, WHICH REFLECT THE REQUIREMENTS OF PROSPECTS

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ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the importance and areas of application of Education Management through modern innovative technologies in our country. In higher education, the use of modern educational technologies, that is, interactive techniques, is widely covered. It was mentioned that interactive techniques teach the reader to more firmly master the knowledge of the requirements, increase the culture of Speech, correctly formulate questions, express his opinion

Keywords: *technology, innovation, skills, technique, creative, volitional, process, information, thought, boomerang, labyrinth, Skorabey, group, competition.*

In the current educational system, a new concept of knowledge acquisition - unconventional education-necessitates the laying of methods of technology. Considering the educational process as a system, its constituent elements include: educational purpose, expected results, teacher, student, educational content, method (method) of Education, the form of education, means of Education, control and assessment. When designing the educational process, the system does not work if one of these elements is left out or not selected correctly, which means that the goal cannot be achieved.

Unlike traditional methods in the organization of educational processes, the assimilation and application of new pedagogical technologies in the educational process is a requirement of the time. In the national program, special attention is paid to this issue. The process of Higher Education requires an innovative approach, the creation of scientific developments and modern technologies from each member of our society, along with the widespread use of innovative technologies, their high degree of strengthening, and the implementation of appropriate measures. In the words of our esteemed leader, “the creation of an innovative mechanism in the worldview of our people is our most important task.

As long as there is no innovation, there will be no competition or development in any area. If we do not widely promote changes in this area to our people, and do not develop skills in people, we will not be able to keep up with the intensity of today's era, and the unparalleled achievements of Science and technology. "Modern innovative technology in the management of higher education is one of the most widely used technologies today. And this is due to the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “on education” and the “national program of training”¹, the development of Higher Education combines their goals and objectives with tobra.

Modern innovative technologies in the management of higher education should implement a unified state policy in the field of education and education of the perfect generation, timely and creative solutions to the issues posed, and ensure that the work efficiency of all educational institutions is increased in accordance with the requirements of the present time. This is a complex process, which, in addition to being the task of all state and public organizations, naturally, requires, first of all, a radical, repeated consideration of the content of the activities of institutions of the continuing education system. All this is of particular importance in the development and development of Higher Education. For this, the management and development of education can be organized in accordance with the established procedure at the expense of voluntary contributions of legal entities and individuals, including foreign legal entities and individuals.

The Ministry of higher and secondary special education manages and directs all universities, vocational-technical schools, and educational institutions. Develops and approves curricula and programs for higher education and vocational education. The management of work related to higher education is planned in advance from the bottom to the top, harmonizing with the work process in all areas of education and determining the content of work of all educational institutions. Various innovative methods are widely used in the management process. The correct introduction of innovative technology in the educational process leads to the fact that the teacher acts in this process as the main organizer or consultant. And this is due to the fact that classes in which students are more independent, creative and volitional qualities are formed require their independent thinking, making it possible to express their attitude to the life achievements and problems of young people.

¹ Mirziyoyev Sh.M. “Harakatlar strategiyasi” 2017-2021 yillarga mo`ljallangan besh ustuvor yo`nalishi. – T.: Gofur G`ulom. 2017 yil. g.s. 136

Unconventional learning technology is interpreted differently from the point of view of most scientists. In Particular, T.N.Ballo’s non-traditional education describes technology as “a specific system project to be put into practice”, and focuses on the preliminary design of the educational pedagogical process. V.I. Davudova notes that non-traditional education technology should be “an independent science aimed at solving such issues as the manufacturer of methods that advance certain principles between science and practice, their consistent application.”²

For example, in the educational manual “applied foundations of pedagogical technologies” Q. Tolipov gave the following definition of interactive methods and their description: “one of the important requirements for the Organization of modern training is to achieve high results in a short time, without excessive mental and physical effort. Between a short time, the delivery of certain theoretical knowledge to students, the formation of skills and abilities in certain activities in them, as well as the control of students’ activities, the assessment of the level of knowledge, skills, and abilities acquired by them requires a high pedagogical skill from the teacher and a new approach to the educational process.”

One of our authors R. Ishmuhamedov argues that “the types of interaction of interactive methods that ensure the effective and consequential functioning of the pedagogical process should be organized into groups: teacher-student; student-student; teacher-student; student - Student; Teacher - Student; Non-Traditional education, in my opinion, is a social order arising from the need for technology, a pedagogical process consisting of designing a learning process based on the innovative processes taking place at the present time, to solve the problems before the educational system, new information is needed, capable of assessing this information by themselves, making the necessary decision independent and free-thinking individuals. In this regard, the role and importance of Higher Education in the management jar of innovative technologies are immeasurable³. Innovation (English-innovation) means innovation, innovation. Innovative technologies are innovations, changes in the pedagogical process and the creative activity between the teacher and the student, in the implementation of which mainly interactive methods are used, since the role of Management in education is played by the teacher.

Interactive methods include “Seminar competition” technology “dating” technology, “Zinama-zina” technology, “brainstorming” technology, “Charkhpalak”

² Karimov I.A. Yuksak manaviyat – yengilmas kuch. – T.: Ma`naviyat 2008 yil.

³ Ishmuhammedov R.J. Innovatsion texnologiyalar yordamida ta`lim samaradorligini oshirish yo`llari. Toshkent.: 2005

technology, “cluster” technology, “Boomerang” technology, “3x4” technology, “resume” technology, “problem” technology, “Labyrinth” technology, “Blitz survey” technology, “FSMU” technology, “Skorabey” technology, “Yelpich” Technology, “Communication” Technology, “Matchmaking” technology, “Shorari” technology and others enter. For example, the organization of classes in technology” Seminar competition ” has been widely used in education for many years. This method increases the interest and activity of students. To prepare for this method, students are warned in advance and the topic is published. The student group is divided into 2 subgroups. Each of them must prepare questions on the topic. At the beginning of Seminar, students are introduced to the conditions of the competition. In this case, certain points are set not only for the answers, but also for the correctness and accuracy of the questions, and for additional corrections⁴.

And for all group students to actively participate, minus (-) points can also be indicated, for example, the method of subtracting points for incorrect answers and questions from +3 to -3 can be used. Points scored on the board can be recorded during the competition. At the end of the Seminar, the participants of the winning group can be encouraged with additional points. The educator, as a supervisor of the educational process, must be very vigilant and hear meticulous answers, and give an assessment to each student⁵. This method teaches knowledge to be acquired more firmly, to increase the culture of speech, to correctly structure questions, to express one's opinion.

In the current educational system, a new concept of knowledge acquisition - unconventional education-necessitates the laying of methods of technology. Considering the educational process as a system, its constituent elements include: educational purpose, expected results, teacher, student, educational content, method (method) of Education, the form of education, means of Education, control and assessment. When designing the educational process, the system does not work if one of these elements is left out or not selected correctly, which means that the goal cannot be achieved.

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⁴ Xudoyqulov X.J. Pedagogik texnologiya ta`lim samaradorligining asosidir. Toshkent. Navro`z. 2012

⁵ Sibirskaya M.P. Профессиональное обучение: Педагогические технологии. – Санкт-Петербург. 2002 г. О`

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